
Open government data: usage trends and metadata quality

Journal of Information Science
XX(X):1–44
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DOI: 10.1177/ToBeAssigned
www.sagepub.com/

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Abstract

Open Government Data (OGD) has the potential to support social and economic progress. However, this potential can be frustrated if this data remains unused. Although the literature suggests that OGD datasets metadata quality is one of the main factors affecting their use, to the best of our knowledge, no quantitative study provided evidence of this relationship. Considering about 400,000 datasets of 28 national, municipal, and international OGD portals, we have programmatically analyzed their usage, their metadata quality, and the relationship between the two. Our analysis has highlighted three main findings. First of all, regardless of their size, the software platform adopted, and their administrative and territorial coverage, most OGD datasets are underutilized. Second, OGD portals pay varying attention to the quality of their datasets' metadata. Third, we did not find clear evidence that datasets usage is positively correlated to better metadata publishing practices. Finally, we have considered other factors, such as datasets' category, and some demographic characteristics of the OGD portals, and analyzed their relationship with datasets usage, obtaining partially affirmative answers.

Keywords

Open Government Data usage, Metadata quality, FAIR compliance

Introduction

Open Government Data^I (OGD), data which traditionally originates from governments¹, usually refers to public records (e.g. on transportation, infrastructures, education, health, environment) that can be reused and redistributed by anyone either for free or at a marginal cost. Access and free use of government data are believed to support unprecedented social and economic developments^{2,3}. A study commissioned by European Commission and carried out by Deloitte foresees that the total direct economic value of public sector information is expected to increase from 52 billion in 2018 up to 215 billion by 2028⁴ (p.402). OGD have found application in many sectors, such as environmental protection, security, mobility, and agriculture, and several success stories report promising aspects, thus promoting the spread of best practices that can be adopted in other similar contexts⁵⁻⁷.

However, many administrations still rely on the number of published datasets to measure the success of their Open Data programs⁸, although these numbers say nothing about datasets' quality or their actual reuse^{8,9}. Moreover, although the exponential growth of OGD offers consumers an enormous amount of data, it also forces them to question the value of these sources, often unknown, in meeting their information needs, curbing their use⁹. This fact leaves the data providers with the uncomfortable feeling that a large part of their data remains unused^{10,11}. This concern transpires in the reports of some US Chief Data Officers presented in¹², with some civic leaders claiming that: "We counted the clicks and we saw that these portals just weren't being used." (n.p)^{II}. Although OGD are considered a driving force for transparency^{13,14} and for stimulating economic growth⁹, they have limited value if not utilized¹⁵. On the other hand, knowledge about Open Data use is scarce, with few studies addressing citizen usage of OGD^{16,17}. These observations were anecdotally reinforced in the course of our past activities¹⁸, where, having accessed to various Open Data portals, we often noticed that much of their datasets are

^I<http://www.oecd.org/gov/digital-government/open-government-data.htm>

^{II}No page - Retrieved online: <https://www.govtech.com/data/Are-Open-Data-Efforts-Working.html>

little used. For these reasons, in¹⁹ we have provided a first evaluation of the use of OGD datasets, based on a sample of national portals. From our analysis, we have drawn two conclusions. Most of the portals examined lack any information on the use of the published datasets. For the few portals publishing programmatically retrievable usage data, we found that most of the datasets are largely unused. We reached a similar conclusion in²⁰ recently, after investigating the usage trends of more than 6,000,000 open research items published on the Figshare^{III} research repository. Also, in this case, the majority of them, almost independently by the scientific discipline they belong, are far from been used.

Among the main barriers and impediments that hinder the success of Open Data initiatives, the low information quality of datasets^{6,9,21-24} and their metadata^{25,26} is often mentioned. The W3C Data on the Web Best Practices (DWBP)^{IV} Working Group by supplying a broad view about how metadata should be published when sharing data on the Web, warns that metadata should help “human users and computer applications” understanding “the data as well as other important aspects that describe a dataset or a distribution” (*Best Practice 1: Provide metadata*). Accordingly, several scholars in the field²⁵⁻²⁹, considering that metadata is the building block of Open Data catalogs, have stressed the importance of providing adequate metadata that allows users to discover, access, and reuse datasets. For instance, Braunschweig et al.²⁷ affirm that “Without sufficient metadata ... neither manual nor automatic search can find the dataset and it will not be helpful for any user” (p. 2), while Zuiderwijk et al.²⁵ observe that “it is essential for the correct interpretation and use of Open Data to offer sufficient metadata simultaneously to data” (p. 120), and Reiche et al.²⁸ argue that “The discoverability is bound to the quality of the metadata” and, consequently, “it is desirable to have high quality metadata.” (p. 236). In the same vein, the FAIR principles strongly envisage the provision of rich and adequate metadata to make OGD datasets fully traceable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable for both humans and machines²⁹. Despite these arguments, to the best of our knowledge,

^{III}<https://figshare.com>

^{IV}<https://www.w3.org/TR/dwbp/>

neither these nor other works provide empirical evidences of a relationship between the quality of the (meta)data and the use of OGD datasets. This fact, is noted by Sadiq and Indulska in¹⁰ (p. 153) suggesting that “the relationship between data quality (...) and the effective use of data remains unexplored in academic literature”, and pointing out that “there is a critical need (...) for empirical testing to identify the contexts and factors that affect the effectiveness of Open Data use”. We provided in²⁰ a contribution in this research direction by empirically exploring the relationship between the usage of open research datasets published on Figshare and the quality of their metadata. Our findings showed no evidence that the latter affects the former.

Guided by these observations, in this paper we take a step forward in investigating possible causes of the apparent low usage of (a large part of) OGD datasets. After collecting programmatically, via Application Program Interface (API), the metadata of almost 400,000 datasets belonging to a sample of 28 national, municipal, and international OGD portals, we analyzed the datasets usage trends, their metadata quality, and the relationship between the two.

The first contribution of this work is an updated description of the use of open datasets belonging to a composite sample (both in size and in the administrative and territorial coverage) of OGD portals. Our findings confirm what we previously noted: although with relevant differences between the portals, datasets are barely or never used.

The second contribution is a quality assessment of the portals of our sample, carried out employing two methodologies focusing respectively, on the quality of datasets metadata, following the approach proposed by Neumaier et al. in²⁶; and on their compliance with the FAIR principles³⁰. The results showed the portals achieve varying degrees of quality of their datasets’ metadata.

The third contribution is the comparison between datasets usage and the quality of their metadata and toward their compliance with FAIR principles. In both cases, the statistical analysis did not reveal a clear positive correlation between datasets usage and their metadata quality.

We, finally, explored other factors that may direct users’ choice towards some datasets instead of others. We ascertained, at the

dataset level, the possible role of belonging to a thematic category. We also investigated, at the portal level, whether demographic factors (i.e. city population, portal size) can characterize the propensity of some city portals to be more used than others.

Background

In their 2012 study Janssen et al.⁹ concluded that “achieving the success of Open Data systems depends to a large extent on *the use and the quality* [emphasis added] of the data provided” (p. 266). Almost ten years later, several theoretical studies and technological solutions have been proposed regarding the quality assessment of Open (Government) Data. However, little has been done to (quantitatively) analyze their actual use. Nor, to our knowledge, the relationship between the quality of OGD and their use has been examined in detail.

OGD portals

By adopting dedicated software platforms, the OGD portals make public data available under the release policies in force in their administrations. Through these platforms, portal managers publish their datasets, assigning specific metadata with which to organize them into categories. Based on these metadata, users can access the data of their interest through more or less advanced search and browsing functionalities. These platforms usually provide APIs with which it is possible to programmatically query the portals to download both metadata and datasets³¹. Among the platforms adopted in OGD portals, the open-source CKAN and the commercial Socrata stand out in number^{31,32}.

A key feature distinguishing the CKAN portals from the Socrata ones is that the latter allow users directly visualize the datasets of their catalog in a tabular form via a browser. These tables can further be downloaded in different formats. By contrast, in CKAN-based portals, the actual content is not (generally) immediately displayed by the browser.

OGD quality and use

From database systems to multimedia information delivered by Web technologies, poor data quality affects information retrieval, knowledge discovery and data reuse³³. Data quality is acknowledged as a “multifaceted concept”³⁴ (p. 6) involving different dimensions (e.g. correctness, completeness, relevancy, availability, consistency). Several methodological frameworks and technological proposals have been defined to evaluate the various quality dimensions of information resources, appropriately measured by quality metrics^{35–40}. More recently, some of these works focused on assessing and monitoring Open Data portals’ performance, taking into exam the quality of the data as well as of the associated metadata. Almost all these works clearly highlight deficits in metadata quality^{26–28}, pointing out that most of the evaluated datasets lacked metadata^{15,41} or presented a naive version of them⁴². Looking at specific factors affecting OGD data and metadata quality, Vetró et al.⁴¹ found that centralized (i.e. with standardized data structures) data disclosure yields better quality data and metadata than decentralized (i.e. no common data structure). Máchová and Lnenicka¹⁵ observed that national portals powered by CKAN achieved better quality scores than the others, by contrast, according to⁴³, US cities’ Socrata based portals show better performance based on their portal overall score. The population of the city is deemed to affect OGD portals qualitative performance^{43,44}. Based on their findings some authors make suggestions to improve OGD portals effectiveness, by recommending the creation of automatic evaluation platforms, thus to constantly monitor OGD metadata quality^{26,28,32}; by suggesting that the results of the quality assessments are used to improve the performance of the OGD portals, to make them more usable and therefore increasing their adoption¹⁵; by encouraging portal managers to make better use of their platforms for greater user participation⁴³. Finally Zhu et al.⁴³ conclude that “more research is needed to understand who actually uses the portals and the data, and for what purposes” (p. 36).

None of these works provide empirical evidence of a relationship between (metadata) quality and OGD datasets usage. Nor is this relationship considered in papers that have focused on other barriers

to the release of OGD^{21,22}. At present, only a limited number of studies have examined data on user experience. In their survey Safarov, Meijer, and Grimmelikhuijsen¹¹ highlighted that most of the examined studies focus on aspects related to the release of OGD, taking for granted, but not empirically testing, the use in its various forms. They urge empirical analysis researches to evaluate “if the estimated effects of OGD are actually measurable.” (p. 16). Wirtz, Weyerer and Rösch¹⁷ found that citizens’ intention to use OGD is primarily driven by their usefulness, and that collaboration is a usage motivating factor, as well as is the ease-of-use (i.e. the effort required to consume OGD) of OGD enabling platforms. Lassinantti, Stahlbröst and Runardotter¹⁶ carried out a document analysis to clarify what motives urge people to use OGD, and what important users types exist. They identified five main relevant social groups according to the motives that drive people towards Open Data use: i) exploring for creativity; ii) creating business value; iii) enabling local citizen value; iv) addressing global societal challenges; v) advocating the Open Data agenda. Ruijter, Grimmelikhuijsen, van den Berg and Meijer⁴⁵ posit that “in order to better understand the complexity of OGD usage” (p. 6), it is necessary to examine the interactions between governments and citizens on OGD platforms and what “people actually do with Open Data’ (p. 2) in their daily lives. They observed a discrepancy between user needs and what is offered by the existing datasets, and pointed out, that “A more participatory approach to the development of OGD platforms is needed to prevent a situation where there are great technological opportunities but no usage” (p. 14). These works, analysing the use of OGD, theoretically or based on empirical research focused on surveys, achieve qualitative conclusions on the type of users, their motivations, and the relationships between them. However, besides our mentioned paper¹⁹, to the best of our knowledge, the only other work providing quantitative analysis on the use of OGD datasets, dates back to 2014 and focused on 20 US Socrata-based city⁴⁶. The reported results, on the trend of the number of views, agree with those we found in¹⁹.

Material and Methods

The main objective of this work is to analyze the use of open government datasets, the quality of their metadata, and the relationship between the two. Furthermore, in light of the current literature, we examine other factors that can influence the use of OGD datasets. Accordingly, the research questions guiding this study are: RQ1: Which are the forms of OGD datasets usage?; RQ2: Which are the OGD datasets' metadata quality and compliance to FAIR principles, as assessed by two existing tools?; RQ3: Do the OGD datasets' metadata quality and compliance to FAIR principles affect datasets usage?; RQ4: Does the OGD datasets categorization influence their use?; RQ5: Can some OGD portals' demographic features drive users' attention towards their datasets?

To answer these questions our experimental investigation first identified the metrics to measure datasets usage and the criteria for selecting the 28 OGD portals. The collection and processing phase was carried out programmatically. For each selected portal we have extracted its datasets' usage information, and we have assessed its datasets metadata quality and their compliance with the FAIR principles.

Usage Metrics

According to Dawes, Vidiiasova, and Parkhimovich⁴⁷ “Data use includes activities to search, identify, and download data for a variety of purposes including analysis and application development” (p. 18). However, monitoring the use of datasets as well as which applications use them is still an open challenge⁴⁸. Therefore, to get insights on the data demand by users we analyzed two parameters sometimes associated with datasets in some portals: the total number of views and the total number of downloads^{46,49–51}. We mean by *Views* the total number of times the Web page of a dataset has been loaded in users' browsers and by *Downloads* the total number of users' requests for retrieving the full content of a particular dataset⁵² (Table 1). These values, that can be found on the dataset access page and returned by portal API, supply an indicator of use for the activities of *direct users*, i.e. those users who consult a dataset directly¹¹.

Table 1. Usage metrics: definitions and references

Metric	Definition	Source
Views	Total number of times the Web page of a dataset has been loaded in users' browsers	49
Downloads	Total number of users' requests for retrieving the full content of a particular dataset	52

Views and Downloads can certainly help measure the impact of OGD⁵³ initiatives but they are not exhaustive. In fact, several government portals encourage other forms of OGD use⁵⁴ through the provision of data analytics tools⁵⁵, the deployment of citizen services⁵⁶, or publication of reports based on OGDs. A more focused usage indicator should, for example, evaluate the number of these *indirect users*, together with the number of these applications¹¹. However, if it can be difficult to collect and directly assign to a dataset the number of users of an application^{48,54}, the applications reusing a given dataset could be gathered as done by the French^V and Portuguese^{VI} portals. This parameter could help improve the perception of datasets' usefulness, also providing an indicator for the evaluation of the indirect use of the portal. To facilitate this recognition, third-party applications that use a dataset should always be encouraged to cite it among their sources⁵⁷. In addition to facilitating the discovery of data and supporting the monitoring of its impact and its reuse, data citation^{VII} helps users to know the provenance of the original data, thus making the products of these applications more reliable³⁹.

Portals selection and data collection

The experimental investigation considered three types of OGD portals based on their administrative coverage: national, municipal, and international. Among these portals, we have selected those that publish usage information, in particular the number of datasets' views and downloads, and which have APIs for programmatic retrieval of this information.

^V<https://www.data.gouv.fr/en/reuses/>

^{VI}<https://dados.gov.pt/en/reuses/>

^{VII}<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/#data-citation>

As for the national portals, we initially considered the 94 countries ranked, in 2017, by Global Open Data Index (GODI)^{VIII} based on their publication practices of Open Data. To these, we added Korea, Spain, Ireland, and Estonia, not included by GODI, but ranked by the OURdata Index^{IX} performed by OECD. Among these 98 portals, we first selected the 15 portals that display at least one usage metric for each dataset. From these, we further picked the eight portals providing APIs to collect the usage values programmatically (Table 2).

Following a similar approach, we have selected 16 US municipal portals. Our choice to focus on US city portals, besides the fact that many of these city governments were among the first to adhere to Open Data practices⁵⁸, under the government's impetus by President Obama, is due to the interest showed towards these portals in the literature. In fact, in recent years, following the considerable efforts made by US cities to publish Open Data and encourage citizens to use them^{43,46}, several scholars have investigated their characteristics^{8,59,60} and analyzed their performance^{43,44,46}. For example, Zhu et al.⁴³, in a study on 34 US cities, found that the city population is positively related both to the number of its portal's datasets as well to an overall score based on a set of portal-level metrics they defined and manually tested. A strong correlation between the number of datasets available for a city and its population was also verified by Barbosa et al.⁴⁶ in the case of 20 US municipalities. Similar results have been reported by Thorsby et al.⁴⁴ in a study on a set of 37 US cities portals, that found population size was related both to the number of portals' datasets, and on an 'Open Government Data Portal Index', based on some features of Open Data portals, designed and manually evaluated by the authors. Based on the results that emerged from these studies, we deemed it appropriate to contribute with an analysis of these portals' usage, also examining its relationship with their metadata quality. Table 2 shows that these portals are mainly based on Socrata, which is, in fact, the most used software platform by US cities³².

The sample of four international portals considered, albeit small, can be deemed of significant public utility and interest, thanks to the heterogeneity of the thematic coverage offered by the datasets of

^{VIII}<https://index.okfn.org/>

^{IX}<http://www.oecd.org/gov/digital-government/open-government-data.htm>

these portals in the financial, aerospace, legislative and humanitarian sectors. The Humanitarian data exchange portal (HDX) promoted by the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs is aimed at sharing data on the areas of crisis in the world, thus supporting humanitarian aid organizations in making “quick, life-saving and informed decisions”^X. The European Union Open Data Portal (EUODP) primarily aimed at EU citizens and organizations, gives access to more than 14,000 datasets published by EU institutions, agencies, and bodies. The DATA.NASA.GOV catalog collects and makes available for the public about 10,000 NASA datasets, aggregating data harvested from different archives (e.g. Planetary Data System, National Oceanographic and Atmospheric Agency,...). Although available to everyone, this portal primarily targets at space and environment scientists. The Open Finances portal makes available public financial data and portfolio information from across all World Bank Group’s entities in one place.

The data have been collected in the period 18th December 2019 to 3rd January 2020. These data provide a snapshot of the overall use of the datasets of the 28 portals, in terms of Views and Downloads, up to that moment. We have published the data from these portals and the analyzes carried out in this study as Open Data in the Zenodo Open Data repository⁶¹

Methods

Gathering Usage Information By means of Python code, we retrieved the portals usage data by appropriately exploiting the metadata discovery APIs provided by the various portals’ platforms. Each dataset’s metadata content was then extracted and stored in an internal database for subsequent analysis. The various discovery and retrieval APIs act as follows.

The CKAN API provides information relating to the number of views in a `tracking_summary` metadata field, containing two values: `total` and `recent` (i.e. Views in the last 14 days). According to the definition of the Views metric in Table 1, we took the `total` value for our analysis. It must be said that the presence of usage information,

^X<https://news.un.org/en/audio/2018/12/1028891>

Table 2. Demographic characteristics of national, municipal and international OGD portals. Software platform adopted and the usage metrics available V (View), D (Downloads) or O (Others) are reported. Nationals and US cities populations are gathered respectively from the United Nations* and the US Census** portals

Portal	Datasets	Platform	Metrics	Population ¹
US	261,514	CKAN	V	331,002
France	39,412	Other	V,O	65,273
Colombia	9,795	Socrata	V,D	50,883
IE	9,598	CKAN	V	4,937
Slovenia	4,892	CKAN	V	2,078
Poland	1,032	Other	V	37,846
Latvia	336	CKAN	V	1,886
Puerto Rico	178	Socrata	V,D	2,860
New York, NY	2,771	Socrata	V,D	8,398
Baltimore, MD	2,617	Socrata	V,D	602
Austin, TX	2,353	Socrata	V,D	964
Chicago, IL	1,368	Socrata	V,D	2,705
San Francisco, CA	1,001	Socrata	V,D	883
Dallas, TX	1,001	Socrata	V,D	1,345
Los Angeles, CA	943	Socrata	V,D	3,990
Seattle, WA	718	Socrata	V,D	744
Providence, RI	288	Socrata	V,D	179
Honolulu, HI	244	Socrata	V,D	347
New Orleans, LA	215	Socrata	V,D	391
Buffalo, NY	213	Socrata	V,D	256
Nashville, TN	172	Socrata	V,D	669
Boston, MA	170	CKAN	V	694
Albuquerque, NM	60	CKAN	V	560
Albany, NY	50	Socrata	V,D	97
HDX	17,325	CKAN	V,D	-
EUODP	14,058	CKAN	V	-
NASA	9,664	Socrata	V,D	-
World Bank Finances	2,177	Socrata	V,D	-

¹ In thousands

* <https://population.un.org/wpp/Download/Standard/Population/>

** <https://factfinder.census.gov/faces/tableservices/jsf/pages/productview.xhtml?src=CF>

in the GET response, is not guaranteed by default but has to be explicitly requested in the GET call, and has to be enabled server side^{XI}. Besides, not all CKAN based portals return usage metadata in the `tracking_summary` field. Instead, as in the case for the IE, EUODP,

^{XI}<https://docs.ckan.org/en/2.8/maintaining/tracking.html>

and the HDX portals, usage information is contained in other fields or slightly different metadata structures. Furthermore, there are cases, such as the HDX portal, based on a CKAN extension, in which the metadata recovery API returns, in addition to the number of views, also the total downloads.

The RESTfull Socrata Open Data API (SODA^{XII}) allows retrieving datasets metadata but returns a different and somehow smaller set of metadata fields compared to the ones retrieved by CKAN. For instance, the downloadable formats of dataset content are not reported. Conversely to CKAN, SODA metadata returns usage information without having to explicitly require for that. Furthermore, this information includes, in addition to the total number of views (`page_views`) also the total number of downloads (`download_count`) at the current date.

Finally, some portals, like the French and Polish, use other software platforms, which provide different APIs than CKAN and Socrata, both in the call format and in the type of information returned. In particular, the French portal, returns the total number of views at the current date, in the API JSON response (in a sub-field named `views`), but not in the metadata visible to users. Besides, the API returns two other usage indicators namely `Reuse number` and `Number of followers`.

Evaluating metadata quality According to Batini et al. data quality is “a multifaceted concept” (p. 6) involving several dimensions³⁴, where a *quality dimension* can be seen as a set of “quality attributes that represents a single aspect or construct of data quality”, as observed by Wang et al.³⁵(p. 6). A *quality metric* serves to measure a specific aspect of a given dimension. Quality dimensions and metrics are central at evaluating whether a piece of data meets the information users’ needs in a specific situation⁶². However, while methodological frameworks^{35,63} and surveys^{34,38} provide theoretical background and general guidelines to deploy data quality assessments in several fields^{41,62,64}, as observed by Reiche et al.²⁸ it is crucial the availability of data quality platforms to monitor “the quality of different public government data repositories” (p. 241). To develop our quantitative analysis on OGD portals, driven by our five research

^{XII}<https://dev.socrata.com/>

questions, we sought already tested solutions quickly integrable with our code for portals usage retrieval. Therefore, as to the metadata quality assessment, we relied on the ‘Open Data Portal Watch’ platform code^{XIII} presented by Neumaier et al.²⁶, which implements a “concrete computation and automated assessment of quality metrics based on the DCAT metadata schema” (p. 23). At the core of the platform implementation, there is a mapping between the heterogeneous datasets metadata, retrieved by APIs from the OGD portals, and the W3C DCAT^{XIV} vocabulary. The platform implements 17 quality metrics (see Table 8 in Appendix for the complete list) to assess the compliance of ingested metadata with DCAT requirements. These metrics concern three quality dimensions: i) *Existence*, i.e. do specific metadata fields exist?; ii) *Conformance*, i.e. do metadata values adhere to a certain format?; iii) *Data Open*, i.e. may the specified format and license information classify a dataset as open?. The eight *Existence* metrics evaluate if metadata supply useful information to discover (i.e. is there a dataset description, a title, some keywords?) and access (i.e. are there URIs to access and download?) the associated dataset, to contact the owner or the publisher. The presence of license information is also evaluated, as well as the dates of creation and modification of the metadata and the dataset. The *Preservation* metric assesses the existence of metadata information regarding the format, size and the update frequency of the datasets. The *Spatial* and *Temporal* metrics^{XV} ascertain if some spatial (e.g. polygon, shape,...) or temporal (e.g. start or end of the period of the time covered by the dataset) information exists. The six *Conformance* metrics assess the syntactical validity of the access URI, the contact email address and URI, and the date format; the license conformance is checked by analyzing a list of license descriptions provided by the Open Definition^{XVI}; and the validity of the file format is checked against a list of registered formats and media types supplied by IANA^{XVII}. As to the three *Data Open* metrics they ascertain

^{XIII}<https://github.com/sebneu/portalwatch>

^{XIV}<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dcat-2/>

^{XV} Declared and implemented only in the framework code

^{XVI}<https://licenses.opendefinition.org/licenses/groups/all.json>

^{XVII}<http://www.iana.org/assignments/media-types/media-types.xhtml>

the datasets compliance to the Open (Knowledge) Definition^{XVIII}, assessing if the datasets are supplied in a machine readable and open format, and according to an open license.

The quality assessment has been carried out on each portals' dataset, resulting in a single, boolean, or floating (in the $[0,1]$ range), qv value for each metadata quality metric. For each dataset, after converting boolean values into 0 and 1, we aggregated the 17 metrics according to the Simple Additive Weighting (SAW) decision-making method, by assigning equal weight ($w_j = 1/17$) to every metric, thus resulting in a dataset *overall metadata quality* value $omq = \sum_{j=1}^{17} qv_j * w_j$, $omq \in [0, 1]$. For each dataset, we stored its computed omq value in an internal database along with the metadata and usage information. The 'Open Data Portal Watch' platform code was integrated with our usage extraction code and extended to elaborate and produce analytic and reporting.

We point out that, to give an image as analytical as possible of the quality of the portals and their use, the quality assessment that we have carried out is intrinsically objective (aka structural), measurable through impartial physical characteristics (e.g. item counts, ratios) of the OGD portals⁶⁵. It has ignored subjective (aka contextual) aspects, capable of taking into account users' needs and purposes and informing their usage choices^{39,65}, but which are out of the scope of an experimental investigation such as that proposed by us, that programmatically evaluates a large number of datasets, belonging to different public administrations and organizations, based on their metadata.

As a final remark, we point out that the 'Open Data Portal Watch' platform was designed and implemented based on the previous version of W3C DCAT. For this reason, it does not evaluate some new properties introduced in the 2020 revision that extends the original DCAT vocabulary. In particular, following DWBP practices Five and Six, which recommend publishing datasets by providing provenance and quality metadata, the new version of DCAT supplies "more details for the ways of representing dataset provenance and quality". In the first case suggesting using the W3C Provenance

^{XVIII}<http://opendefinition.org/od/2.1/en/>

Ontology (PROV-O)^{XIX}, in the second employing the W3C Data Quality Vocabulary (DQV)^{XX}. In our previous work³⁹, we exemplified the adoption of these two technologies by providing W3C compliant metadata to document the quality assessment of a set of e-Government controlled vocabularies.

Assessing compliance with FAIR Based on the FAIR principles²⁹, Wilkinson et. al. have designed a framework³⁰ and developed a ‘FAIR Evaluator’^{XXI} tool implementing a series of metrics to test the compliance of a Web resource with those principles. We rely on such a tool to check how (a sample of) the selected OGD portals support the “machines to automatically find and use”²⁹ (p. 1) the published datasets, “in addition to supporting its reuse by individuals”²⁹ (p. 1). The framework implements ‘22 Maturity Indicators Tests’, grouped by the four principles respectively, in eight (Findable), five (Accessible), seven (Interoperable), and two (Reusable) (see Table 9 in Appendix). The tool allows users to select the whole 22 tests, or one of the four subgroups, for assessing the FAIRness of a given (Web) resource by supplying its Globally Unique Identifier (GUID). At the end of the evaluation process, an assessment report summarizes the successes and failures of the resource for the selected metrics. Users may interact with the evaluator either directly by Web interface or via APIs.

Following the latter option, we submitted a sample of the selected OGD datasets, gathered the evaluation results metadata, and extracted from them the values of interest, finally integrating them with the other datasets metadata stored on our internal database. The integration and normalization step has been made following the same approach presented in previous section.

The decision to carry out the compliance assessment on a sample rather than on all the 400,000 datasets is due to the long waiting times required to perform a single dataset assessment. In fact, after performing several checks on datasets belonging to different portals, we realized that the waiting time for each evaluation carried out (on the 22 available tests) by the ‘FAIR Evaluator’ tool was never less than

^{XIX}<https://www.w3.org/TR/prov-o>

^{XX}<https://www.w3.org/TR/vocab-dqv/>

^{XXI}<https://fairsharing.github.io/FAIR-Evaluator-FrontEnd>

5 minutes with peaks of 30 minutes or more. The reason for this delay is probably because, for every single dataset GUID, a series of multiple calls to remote sites^{XXII} is necessary to check if a given element present in the metadata of the dataset conforms to the underlying principle. For this reason, we restricted our analysis to a subset of our initial sample, consisting of US citizen portals. However, as these portals amount to about 15,000 datasets and the expected completion times would have been in the order of weeks, we have given up assessing all these portals' datasets. Instead, we have examined for each portal a sample of 80 datasets taken in a (pseudo) random way considering the number of Views that took place. We then randomly selected 40 datasets among those with the number of Views below the first quartile and 40 above the third quartile. In this way, we have tried to bring out, as far as possible, the potential relationships between the usage of a dataset and its compliance with the FAIR principles.

Results

RQ1: Which are the forms of OGD datasets usage?

Views and Downloads values gathered from the 28 portals provide information about the usage frequencies for their datasets.

Views Figure 1 shows the distribution of the number of Views for all the portals: national, U.S. cities, and international. On the X-axis the number of Views are grouped in five non-linear classes (i.e. 0–10, 10–100, 100–1,000, 1,000–10,000, and >10,000). On the Y-axis is reported the percentage of datasets for each class. We can see that Views are not distributed normally, and that all portals show that just a very low percentage of their datasets is viewed more than a thousand times. By contrast, several of them show very low (10–100) to extremely low (<10) numbers of Views for the great percentage of their datasets. Figure 1 shows that this fact is particular true for six portals, i.e. the ones of the US, France, IE, and Slovenia, as well as the HDX and NASA ones, with more than 90% of their datasets has been viewed no-more than 100 times. These results are further clarified by the Views descriptive statistics (i.e. mean,

^{XXII}<https://github.com/FAIRMetrics/Metrics/tree/master/MaturityIndicators/Gen2>

Figure 1. Overall Views distributions for the National, the US cities and the international OGD portals. The number of Views are grouped into five classes: 0–10, 10–100, 100–1,000, 1,000–10,000, and >10,000.

standard deviation, first, second, and third quartile) listed in Table 3. By examining the first two quartiles we notice that almost the 50% of

Table 3. Portals' overall Views descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, first, second, and third quartile)

	mean	std	1Q	2Q	3Q
US	35	623	2	12	21
France	85	2,114	0	0	1
Colombia	1,223	7,507	99	197	559
IE	54	342	0	3	20
Slovenia	22	174	2	3	12
Poland	822	5,619	101	234	491
Latvia	151	213	44	102	191
Puerto Rico	2,310	9,224	83	295	833
New York, NY	4,989	52,767	109	360	1,276
Baltimore, MD	1,215	6,060	152	336	717
Austin, TX	4,077	24,400	78	332	1,087
Chicago, IL	10,726	5,718	332	1,198	4,614
San Francisco, CA	2,227	10,921	141	458	1,361
Dallas, TX	6,757	86,254	4	145	499
Los Angeles, CA	3,836	13,314	31	260	2,701
Seattle, WA	2,349	11,873	84	237	717
Providence, RI	1,091	5,932	77	178	509
Honolulu, HI	619	1,958	10	89	436
New Orleans, LA	2,991	6,741	131	453	2,191
Buffalo, NY	1,000	1,997	34	169	970
Nashville, TN	3,527	12,499	130	628	1,793
Boston, MA	1,528	3,346	344	656	1,454
Albuquerque, NM	47	33	28	38	62
Albany, NY	607	1,609	11	24	67
HDX	40	247	0	0	26
EUODP	327	1,107	52	212	373
NASA	43	703	8	10	14
World Bank Finances	2,668	6,071	737	1129	2,180

those six portals' datasets is barely viewed by users (with the higher median equal 12 for the US portal), and another 25% just more visited (the higher third quartile is 26 for HDX). This fact is particularly unexpected if considering that these portals belong to countries with not negligible numbers of inhabitants (particularly US and France), with a full-blown tradition of attention to Open Data (i.e. US), or of noticeable interest for the whole scientific community (i.e. NASA). It is worth noting that four out of six of these portals are based on

the CKAN platform, one on the French platform and just one on Socrata (i.e NASA). The views numbers for the other 22 portals are more promising, showing higher values, even by two or three orders of magnitude, for all quartiles. Looking at the median values, the World Bank Finances portal and some US cities' portals, like Chicago, Nashville, Boston, San Francisco, and New Orleans, mostly based on Socrata, achieve quite high numbers.

The values in Table 3 suggest quite clearly that Socrata-based portals are viewed more than others. To test the general hypothesis that differences in the usage of datasets are due to the underlying portals platform, we carried out the Kruskal-Wallis non-parametric test. It analyzes whether the independent variable 'platform' (taking the values 'CKAN', 'Socrata', and 'Others') affects the dependent variable 'number of views'. The values reported by the test execution: $chi - squared = 74,437$, $df = 2$, $p - value < 2.2e - 16$, confirmed the hypothesis. Besides, the post-hoc pairwise test confirmed that there are significant usage differences between all three platforms.

We also checked the hypothesis that differences in the usage of datasets are due to the administrative coverage of their portals. Indeed, nations, municipalities, and international organizations may have different policies or follow diverse administrative operations to publish Open Data. Through Kruskal-Wallis test, we analyzed whether the independent variable 'administrative coverage' (taking the values 'national', 'municipal', and 'international') affects the dependent variable 'number of views'. The test reported values: $chi - squared = 32,762$, $df = 2$, $p - value < 2.2e - 16$, confirmed the hypothesis. The post-hoc pairwise test confirmed that there are significant usage differences between all three types of administration.

Downloads Considering that the number of downloads is not always present for all the 28 portals, we show in Figure 2 the total amount of views and downloads only for the 14 US cities portals based on Socrata that also include the download numbers in the metadata.

We do not show the Downloads distribution graphs, as they follow a similar distribution as the Views. For the same reason and sake of brevity, we do not include detailed statistics of Downloads, although we report that Downloads statistics are in line with those of the

Figure 2. Total number of Views and Downloads (in millions) for 14 US cities Socrata-based portals

Views^{XXIII}. The Downloads values for the three quartiles are always minor than the respective Views. Notwithstanding, for all portals, there is a percentage of datasets with higher number of Downloads than Views (this can explain for instance the two histograms for Chicago in Figure 2). This situation is not inconsistent as reported to us by the Socrata support desk, according to which automatic tools such as bots, or APIs, can be used to autonomously download the datasets, without having to visit the portal sites. We also note that in the case of Chicago the total value of the downloads is heavily influenced by a single dataset^{XXIV}, which has been downloaded over 14 million times but just viewed one-tenth of the time (1,457,673).

^{XXIII}The interested reader is referred to these data to the cited Zenodo dataset⁶¹

^{XXIV}<https://data.cityofchicago.org/Administration-Finance/Current-Employee-Names-Salaries-and-Position-Title/xzkq-xp2w>

RQ2: Which are the OGD datasets' metadata quality and compliance to FAIR principles, as assessed by two existing tools?

Metadata quality assessment As can be seen from Table 4 reporting the descriptive statistics of the overall metadata quality (*omq*), plus the mean values for the three quality dimensions, for the datasets of the 28 portals, it is possible to subdivide the portals essentially into two main groups according to the adopted platform.

Table 4. Descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation, first, second, and third quartile) for the overall metadata quality, and mean quality values for the three quality dimensions.

	mean	std	1Q	2Q	3Q	Existence	Conformance	Open Data
US	0.54	0.12	0.45	0.53	0.64	0.67	0.50	0.25
France	0.64	0.07	0.61	0.62	0.69	0.69	0.67	0.48
Columbia	0.37	0.06	0.33	0.38	0.39	0.49	0.37	0.06
IE	0.69	0.12	0.56	0.70	0.82	0.72	0.68	0.61
Slovenia	0.46	0.02	0.46	0.47	0.47	0.48	0.55	0.26
Poland	0.45	0.09	0.37	0.49	0.51	0.37	0.45	0.67
Latvia	0.75	0.08	0.74	0.75	0.80	0.72	0.77	0.81
Puerto Rico	0.39	0.10	0.27	0.41	0.51	0.44	0.42	0.17
New York, NY	0.29	0.04	0.27	0.27	0.32	0.38	0.30	0.01
Baltimore, MD	0.33	0.03	0.32	0.32	0.33	0.49	0.27	0.01
Austin, TX	0.39	0.11	0.25	0.45	0.50	0.45	0.41	0.20
Chicago, IL	0.32	0.05	0.27	0.33	0.33	0.42	0.33	0.01
San Francisco, CA	0.38	0.02	0.38	0.39	0.39	0.50	0.42	0
Dallas, TX	0.38	0.09	0.32	0.33	0.45	0.43	0.42	0.15
Los Angeles, CA	0.44	0.06	0.44	0.45	0.45	0.49	0.45	0.30
Seattle, WA	0.45	0.05	0.42	0.45	0.50	0.49	0.46	0.32
Providence, RI	0.30	0.07	0.27	0.27	0.32	0.40	0.28	0.05
Honolulu, HI	0.26	0.04	0.26	0.26	0.26	0.36	0.26	0.01
New Orleans, LA	0.38	0.10	0.27	0.44	0.51	0.45	0.40	0.18
Buffalo, NY	0.41	0.08	0.42	0.44	0.45	0.47	0.40	0.26
Nashville, TN	0.46	0.06	0.44	0.50	0.51	0.50	0.49	0.29
Boston, MA	0.65	0.14	0.68	0.69	0.69	0.65	0.58	0.78
Albuquerque, NM	0.56	0.14	0.57	0.59	0.60	0.54	0.61	0.50
Albany, NY	0.39	0.10	0.27	0.44	0.49	0.45	0.41	0.21
HDX	0.59	0.09	0.54	0.63	0.63	0.69	0.50	0.50
EUODP	0.35	0.02	0.34	0.34	0.34	0.55	0.26	0
NASA	0.32	0.02	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.39	0.40	0
World Bank Finances	0.33	0.01	0.33	0.33	0.33	0.51	0.25	0

CKAN-based portals, except for EUODP and Slovenia, show a wider distribution around the mean values all above 0.5. These portals show even higher quality values for the medians and third quartiles (i.e. 0.64 for US, 0.82 for IE, 0.80 for Latvia, 0.69 for Boston, 0.6 for Albuquerque, and 0.63 for HDX). The same behavior is followed by the French portal (median 0.62, 3rd quartile 0.69), while the Polish portal (based on a different platform) shows values spreading around

a 0.45 mean. Conversely, Socrata-based portals have all very similar mean values always under 0.5, with 3rd quartiles under 0.52.

By inspecting the returned metadata, we notice that the main reason for the lower quality values of the Socrata-based portals is related to the less rich metadata returned by the SODA APIs if compared to the metadata fields returned by CKAN and by the French platform. For example, information about the format of the downloadable files is not present in the Socrata metadata. For this reason, the four metrics assessing the existence (*Preservation*), conformity (*FileFormat*), and openness (*OpenFormat* and *MachineRead*) of datasets format always return a value of 0. This is ironic considering that, from a user perspective, Socrata-based portals allow downloading datasets' content in a multitude of formats, thus satisfying one of the golden Open Data rules^{XXV}.

Despite the common platform, there are differences between the Socrata-based portals. Because of the same type of administration, it is interesting to examine the case of US cities, from which one would expect similar quality values, considering that the respective portals can be handled likewise. For some of them, such as New York, Baltimore, and Chicago, the mean and median values are around 0.3, while other portals such as Seattle and Los Angeles have median values around 0.45. By examining the metadata, we realized that this difference largely depends on the presence or absence of license information. In fact, in the case of New York, license information is absent for 97% of the datasets, while more than 96% of Seattle's datasets have this information. Besides for Seattle these licenses are well-formed and open, thus increasing further the total quality value. On the other hand, if we compare the usage statistics for the same two portals (Table 3), we observe that New York has higher values than Seattle for each statistical indicator. This fact may be due to the larger population of the former than the latter. In the next section, trying to answer the research question RQ5, we explore possible relationships between the use of OGD, the city population, and the number of datasets of a portal.

^{XXV} <https://opengovdata.org/>

More generally, looking at how each dimension contributes to the overall quality score, we notice from Table 4 that the *Open Data* dimension presents the lower values. With the sole exception of Ireland, Poland, Latvia, and Boston, with means over 0.5, and, partly, of the France, HDX, and Albuquerque portals, the other OGD portals seem to overlook the importance of fully adhere to the Open Data principles. In other words, 75% of the portals appear to not supply a large part of their datasets according to open and machine-readable formats and through open licenses. Or if they do, they do not declare such information in the datasets' metadata, as discussed in the case of Socrata-based portals for the format information. Altogether 11 portals have an average *Existence* value equal to or greater than 0.5, and as to *Conformance*, this average value is reached (or exceeded) from 8 out of 28 portals. As to the *Existence* dimension, two metrics, i.e. *Access* and *Contact*, outperformed all others with values over 0.9, for all portals, except Poland whose metadata does not contain any URL to download the associated resource files neither any contact information. More than two-thirds of the portals have at least half of their datasets providing discovery information and some kind of license. Dataset creation or modification times are present in at least 50% of the metadata of all portals. Except for four CKAN-based portals (i.e. US, Ireland, Latvia, and Boston), the always zeroing *Spatial* and *Temporal* metrics, contribute heavily to lower the means of the *Existence* dimension. In addition to the actual lack of spatio-temporal information, these null values can depend on the difficulty in identifying such information in the metadata. As noted by Neumaier et al.²⁶, spatio-temporal chunks can be spread into heterogeneously distributed and portal-dependent metadata fields, which are not easily identifiable automatically. The mean values for the *Conformance* dimension are, for 23 out of 28 portals, lower than those of *Existence*, thus suggesting for these portals a possible lack of care, or inattention, in compiling the information in the metadata fields. This fact is confirmed, for instance, by looking at the contact information (i.e. contact email and URL). Only ten portals have at least half of their datasets with a correct contact email address, while just France, Ireland, and Latvia provide some conform URL to contact the datasets provider. Furthermore, only 11 portals have most of the

datasets provided with a compliant license, i.e. a license description that can be mapped on one present in the list of license descriptions provided by the Open Definition.

This analysis highlights that, although the platform’s metadata schema affects the quality results (such as the lack of information for the file format, in the case of Socrata-based portals), it is the responsibility of portal managers and metadata compilers, ensure to supply published datasets with the most accurate and complete description of the metadata.

Metadata FAIRness The boxplots in Figure 3 show the statistics of the absolute number of successes (i.e. number of tests passed) related to the FAIR compliance assessment carried out by applying the 22 metrics (see Table 9), implemented by the ‘FAIR Evaluator’ tool³⁰ on 1120 datasets. No dataset of any portal passed all the 22 tests. Eight, out of fourteen, portals have a median value equal to 9, the other six have higher medians (11, and 14 for five portals). The third quartile is often higher, up to 16 hits for San Francisco and New Orleans (i.e. a 72% success rate).

Figure 3. Descriptive statistics for FAIR metrics compliance, gauged as the number of passed tests, for 1120 datasets of 14 US cities portals

To have a glimpse of the differences in values obtained by the assessment tool, even within a single portal, let us consider two datasets of the New Orleans portal. The first^{XXVI} passed 16 tests while the second^{XXVII} just 9. By comparing the two assessment reports^{XXVIII}, we note that for the first dataset, both the weak and the strong test, that look if the metadata contains an explicit pointer to the license (sub-principle R1.1), succeed. The tests failed for the second dataset by reporting the message ‘No License property was found in the metadata’. A quick look at the datasets’ pages confirms that a ‘CC0 1.0 Universal’ license is supplied with the former, while no license is available for the latter. Similarly, the test checking if the metadata contains the unique identifier to the data (sub-principle F3) found an identifier (i.e. “<https://data.nola.gov/api/views/d2is-2r79/rows.rdf?accessType=DOWNLOAD>”) just for the first dataset.

To get insights on the extent of the results obtained for each FAIR principle, we report in Table 5 the aggregate statistics for the 22 metrics (see Table 9) grouped by the four principles. Table 5 shows both the absolute and relative values of the number of passed tests for each principle. Only the two metrics related to the R(eusable) principle get very low values. The other 20 metrics measuring the compliance to the F(indable), A(ccessible), and I(nteroperable) principles achieve higher values, with a mean of successes of 0.5, median around 0.5 (i.e. 0.5 for F, 0.4 for A, 0.6 for I) and with still higher values, between 60% and 80%, for the datasets in the 3rd quartile. These results show a not contemptible overall degree of compliance with FAIR, even considering that: “Partly FAIR may be fair enough”, as remarked by several of the originals authors of the FAIR principles in⁶⁶ (p.52 and fig. 1 p. 53).

^{XXVI}<https://data.nola.gov/Housing-Land-Use-and-Blight/Accela-Legacy-Hearings/d2is-2r79>

^{XXVII}<https://data.nola.gov/dataset/District-Name/g9mk-xgnj>

^{XXVIII}<https://fairsharing.github.io/FAIR-Evaluator-FrontEnd/#!/evaluations/1913>,
<https://fairsharing.github.io/FAIR-Evaluator-FrontEnd/#!/evaluations/2616>

Table 5. Descriptive statistics for FAIR evaluations of the sample of 1120 datasets of 14 US cities, grouped per principle. Absolute (abs) and relative (rel) round values for the number of passed tests for each principle.

		mean	std	min	1Q	2Q	3Q	max
F	abs	4.3	0.7	1	4	4	5	6
	rel	0.5	0.1	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.6	0.8
A	abs	2.8	0.9	2	2	2	4	4
	rel	0.5	0.2	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.8	0.8
I	abs	3.9	0.9	0	3	4	5	5
	rel	0.5	0.1	0	0.4	0.6	0.7	0.7
R	abs	0.1	0.5	0	0	0	0	2
	rel	0.1	0.2	0	0	0	0	1

Discussion

The first objective of this work was to verify the reception of OGD portals by users, based on a representative set of them (RQ1). Our findings revealed a general trend of low OGD datasets usage, with differences partly due to the specificity of the platforms underlying the portals and to the portals' administrative coverage. Answering to RQ2, we reported relevant differences between the metadata quality of one portal's datasets and another, possibly due to platform implementation choices, and by different portal managers publishing practices.

In the following, we first discuss the implication of those findings by analyzing the relationship between datasets usage and metadata quality (RQ3). Then, to explore other factors that could affect OGD datasets usage, we supply answers to RQ4 (Does the OGD datasets categorization influence their use?) and RQ5 (Can some OGD portals' demographic features drive users' attention towards their datasets?).

RQ3: Do the OGD datasets' metadata quality and compliance to FAIR principles affect datasets usage?

Metadata quality vs. Usage We verified the correlation between the number of views and metadata quality, through the Spearman's rho (ρ) non-parametric test, instead of Pearson test, as that the Views frequencies do not follow a normal distribution (see Figure 1). By

applying Spearman to all the collected datasets, independently by their portals, we obtained a rho value $\rho = -0.32$ with $p = 0$ indicating a low, even if significant, negative correlation. We then analyzed the behavior of rho on the individual portals, and the results reported in (the first column) of Table 6, testify that in some few cases the ρ values are at most close to 0.4 (i.e. Poland, Providence, New Orleans, and Albuquerque), therefore a correlation value generally considered medium-low⁶⁷. However, in most cases, significant values are far lower, often near 0, and for two cases (i.e. Colombia and Puerto Rico) not significant at all. Besides, for the 26 portals with a significant rho, the sign of the correlation is alternatively positive (16) or negative (10).

To get further insights, in Table 6 we also report the correlations between Views and each single quality dimension. The table shows that the ρ values and signs of one dimension to the others varying for each portal, although with a prevalence of positive signs. Besides, also the contribution of each quality dimension to dataset usage seems to vary case-by-case. For instance, the US portal datasets usage is positively related to *Existence* and *Open Data* dimension and inversely with *Conformance*, while the correlation signs of these dimensions invert for HDX. Furthermore, just for eight portals the signs of the three dimensions (with significant ρ) agree: they are all positive for Poland, Dallas, Los Angeles, New Orleans, and Nashville, and all negative for Austin, Buffalo and Albany.

These controversial values indicate that dataset metadata quality, as measured by our approach, is not always positively correlated with their use. Rather, the negative signs suggest that in many cases users prefer viewing datasets with low metadata quality. This result seems to contradict the common assumption that good quality metadata is a prerequisite datasets usage^{26,28}. Indeed, comparing the Views usage statistics (Table 3) and the metadata quality statistics (Table 4), it is clear that the portals most used are those based on Socrata with the sole exception of the NASA portal. One possible reason for Socrata's success is suggested by Barbosa et al.⁴⁶, who noted how the visualization features of this platform allow users to quickly inspect the datasets, in tabular form, using their web browsers (without necessarily having to download it). If the improved usability of Socrata-based portals can facilitate re-visits of datasets,

Table 6. Correlation values between the number of Views and overall metadata quality (*omq*), and between the number of Views and the three quality dimensions for the selected portals. Spearman's ρ values with $p < 0.05$ in bold text

	omq	Existence	Conformance	Open Data
US	-0.055	0.096	-0.147	0.056
France	0.017	-0.020	0	0.042
Colombia	0.007	0.163	-0.047	-0.106
Ireland	0.038	-0.005	0.229	0.052
Slovenia	-0.357	0.228	-0.447	0.398
Poland	0.422	0.509	0.488	0.355
Latvia	0.178	-0.185	0.443	0.141
Puerto Rico	0.119	0.097	0.095	0.153
New York, NY	-0.175	0.306	-0.300	-0.099
Baltimore, MD	0.199	0.199	0.005	0.009
Austin, TX	-0.182	-0.167	-0.201	-0.255
Chicago, IL	-0.207	-0.360	0.076	0.014
San Francisco, CA	0.140	0.143	0.099	-0.250
Dallas, TX	0.283	0.103	0.429	0.116
Los Angeles, CA	0.163	0.080	0.187	0.171
Seattle, WA	0.131	0.019	0.249	0.198
Providence, RI	0.413	0.405	0.064	-0.005
Honolulu, HI	-0.158	-0.166	0.136	0.129
New Orleans, LA	0.402	0.318	0.416	0.347
Buffalo, NY	-0.175	-0.185	-0.373	-0.476
Nashville, TN	0.360	0.272	0.327	0.244
Boston, MA	0.311	-0.058	0.504	0.315
Albuquerque, NM	0.440	0.392	0.192	0.439
Albany, NY	-0.307	-0.463	-0.347	-0.540
HDX	-0.080	-0.349	0.080	-0.141
EUODP	0.192	0.192	0.251	-
NASA	-0.071	0.011	-0.072	0.053
World Bank Finances	0.136	0.153	-0.007	-0.073

or extend user stay, it will not necessarily attract new users to a portal they have never seen before. Unfortunately, we cannot quantify the accuracy of Barbosa et al.'s observation based on the data in our possession, since the reported number of Views also includes re-visits without being able to distinguish them. We hypothesize that a second explanation of the greater use of Socrata-based portals compared to the others, and in any case linked to their direct availability in a tabular form, is due to the presence of structural information in the returned metadata, also visible to users, that describes the structure (i.e. the columns of the table) and

the type of content (i.e. columns description and format) of these tables. This observation resonates with the DWBP *Best Practice 3: Provide structural metadata*, which recommends providing metadata that helps data consumers better understand the meaning of data and its structure, such as human-readable information related to “the properties or columns of the dataset schema” (see also the implementation example^{XXIX}). Structural information will also enable software agents “to automatically process distributions”. However, the seventeen ‘Open Data Portal Watch’ metrics we adopted do not gauge the presence of structural metadata, somehow penalizing the metadata quality evaluation of the Socrata-based portals compared to that of the others that usually lack structural metadata.

Based on these mixed results, we note that, while important, the quality of OGD datasets’ metadata alone cannot fully explain their usage trends. Other factors of a social, political, and not only technological nature, can come into play and deserve to be studied⁶⁸. These factors cannot be analyzed by the type of quantitative investigation we conducted, which, like that of many other authors^{26,41–43}, has based on an objective evaluation⁶⁵ of the quality of the metadata. However, as we observed in⁶², data quality assessment tasks frequently involve providing judgments on some quality dimensions not generally measurable through a procedure alone, but that require qualitative assertions of their importance for a given scenario. For instance, contextual factors concerning users’ needs⁶⁹, competencies and skills⁴⁵ can affect their approach to OGD resources, and hence the resulting number of views and downloads. As discussed in Section ‘Usage Metrics’, our datasets’ usage analysis is based exclusively on direct portal users that we measure with the two metrics Views and Downloads. However, other users who, for their needs, exploit the datasets indirectly, e.g. through services to citizens^{54,56} or data analytic applications⁵⁵ developed by third parties, could be facilitated to discover and access these tools thanks to ad-hoc metadata associated with them.

FAIRness vs. Usage Due to the non-normality of views distribution, we adopted the non-parametric Spearman rho test also to analyze the

^{XXIX}<https://www.w3.org/TR/dwbp/dwbp-example.html#dataset-structural-metadata>

correlation between FAIR compliance and the use of the dataset. By applying Spearman to the 1120 datasets of 14 US cities, independently by their portals, we obtained a rho value $\rho = 0.04$, with $p = 0.17$, indicating no correlation found between FAIR compliance and datasets' popularity. We reached a similar conclusion after having separately analyzed the correlation data of each portal. From Figure 4 we notice that halves portals show no correlation between usage and FAIR compliance, while the seven portals alternate positive (four portals) or negative (three portals) correlation values, ranging from negligible to medium as in the case of New Orleans ($\rho = 0.521$) and Boston ($\rho = 0.571$).

Analogously to what reported for the metadata quality effect on dataset usage, correlation findings seem to suggest that the lack of compliance with, all or a great part of, the FAIR principles does not prevent users to discover an OGD dataset. However, this fact cannot exclude that findability and access problems may arise in the case of an automatic search for information made by a non-human actor. On the sidelines of this discussion, it is interesting to note, as Wilkinson et al. do⁷⁰, that to maximize the discovery and reuse of OGD resources it is useful to adopt metrics to evaluate metadata quality in a FAIR perspective, but “metrics that assess the popularity of a digital resource are not measuring its FAIRness” (p. 6). And yet we believe, following Sasse et al.³¹, that providing information on the popularity of a dataset, also through direct usage measurements such as views and downloads, can attract the interest of users towards a portal.

RQ4: Does the OGD datasets categorization influence their use?

Organizing a portal's datasets into thematic categories is one of the main features that allow the query and navigation of the OGD portals and is implemented by all platforms. However, as noted in the 2017 EU report “Reuse of Open Data”⁷¹, not all categories attract the same attention from users. Usually, the categories with which to describe the activities of a community refer to a few major themes such as transportation, economics, government, education, public safety. Notwithstanding, noticeable variations emerge in the way OGD portals select the number and terminology of the categories with

Figure 4. Correlation between metadata compliance with FAIR principles and the number of Views for 1120 datasets of 14 US cities. Spearman's ρ values with $p < 0.05$ postfixed with *

which to group their datasets⁶⁰. Zencey⁵⁹ analyzing the popularity of the topics among the datasets published by 141 US public bodies noted that “popular datasets varied significantly based on location” (n.p)^{XXX} and that this variation may “expresses local preferences and needs”. Unlike our contribution, their work does not discuss data on

^{XXX}No page - Retrieved online: <https://sunlightfoundation.com/2017/09/11/whos-at-the-popular-table-our-analysis-found-which-open-data-the-public-likes/>

the use of portals, per se, identifying trends based on detailed usage statistics. Furthermore, their work does not mention any of the quality aspects examined in this paper.

In the wake of these results, it makes sense asking whether and to what extent there is a relationship between the use of a dataset and its category. To answer RQ4 we focused on examining the 14 US cities Socrata-based portals, both for a probable similarity of issues inherent in city life, as well as for the use of the same technology for managing the published data⁵⁸. The number of categories of these portals ranges from 3 in Albany to 25 in Nashville, with an average value of 10.4.

To check the hypothesis that differences in the usage of datasets are due to their category we have applied separately the non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test to each portal. The test analyzed whether the independent variable ‘category’ (taking values in the categories list of the portal) affects the dependent variable ‘number of views’. Except for Los Angeles and Buffalo, the results have shown that the differences are significant, and were confirmed for all portals by the post-hoc analysis to check the pairwise difference amongst categories, we carried out by applying the Conover test. To give an idea of the type of differences between categories, we report some usage data for the New York portal, as it is the portal with the highest number of datasets, as well as belonging to the city with the largest population. Figure 5 shows the percentage of datasets, views, and downloads for the twelve categories of the NYC portal.

The figure shows that some category attracts more interest than others. In particular, about two thirds of the total views are concentrate on two categories: *Transportation* (38.7%) and *City Government* (28.4%). Furthermore, for some category the number of downloads is considerably higher than the number of views (e.g. *Social services*, *Public Safety*, *Environment*, *Education*). This fact can be explained in light of what is reported by the Socrata support desk. Furthermore, Figure 5 reveals another interesting fact about the disparity between the number of datasets published and their use. This aspect is particularly evident in the case of *Transportation*, *Public Safety* and *Education*. *Transportation*, representing only 7.8% of the published datasets, is viewed 38.7% of times and downloaded

Figure 5. Percentage of datasets, views, and downloads per category of the NYC portal

22%. *Public safety*, although covering only 3.5% of the total datasets, is downloaded about three times as much (10.1%). On the other hand, *Education*, which covers 33.1% of NYC datasets, is visited only 4.8% times and downloaded just twice 10.8%. These observations highlight how the governments' efforts to release Open Data do not always correspond to proportional users' feedback. Berends et al.⁷¹ after having examined the European data portal' datasets and their reuse, arrived at a similar conclusion, recognizing that there is a “mismatch between available datasets and re-used data”⁷¹ (p. 26).

RQ5: Can some OGD portals' demographic features drive users' attention towards their datasets?

As noted by Conradie and Choenni²¹, cities have invested considerably in the publication of their data and, also with promotional initiatives such as hackathons, they tend to encourage

private and civil actors to use OGD data to develop innovative services. Some previous works aimed at the analysis of US city portals revealed the possible relationship between the number of a portal' datasets and other factors such as its qualitative performance or the population of the city^{43,44,46}. To answer RQ5 we have considered our sample of 16 US cities and analyzed possible correlations between the population of a city, the size of its portal (i.e. the number of datasets), and its datasets usage and their overall metadata quality (*omq*). We have chosen the median value, for the last two parameters, considering it sufficiently robust to denote the usage and quality of a portal. The results are shown in Table 7.

Table 7. Correlation between portals usage and overall metadata quality, and demographic indicators. Spearman ρ correlation values and p for 16 US cities. Spearman's ρ values with $p < 0.05$ in bold text

	ρ	p
Size / Views:	-0.50	0.04
Size / Overallq:	0.09	0.72
Size / Population:	0.19	0.46
Population / Views:	0.15	0.56
Population / Overallq:	0.34	0.18

We found a significant, quite negative, Spearman correlation, $\rho = -0.5$, $p = 0.04$, just between the number of portal datasets and their use. This fact is consistent with the usage values reported in Table 3 where, except for Albuquerque and Albany, the portals with a smaller number of datasets have a higher median number of visits than others. All other tests reported non-significant p-values, suggesting that neither the portal size does influence its metadata quality, nor the city population seems to affect the use of its portal or its quality. Finally, no correlation has been found between portals size and city populations. This fact seems to contradict previous studies^{43,44,46}. We believe that this may be due to two reasons: i) our sample involves fewer cities than that analyzed by other studies; ii) the different data collection times. We think that this second aspect can affect the correlation results if considering that in three to four years the number of datasets of an OGD portal can increase significantly. For instance, the HDX portal doubled the number of datasets from the time of our previous work (March 2019) to the current one (December

2019). The continuous evolution of a portal's number of datasets and its effects on replicating studies has been noted by others⁷².

Conclusions

The open government data paradigm promises to unleash the potential of transparency and participation policies and to support economic and social development actions. However, many scholars stigmatize that portal managers still paid little attention to the quality of published datasets and associated metadata, as well as to their reuse, also claiming that low quality can hamper OGD usage. To shed light on these aspects that are crucial to understanding the progress of OGD policies, we carried out an exploratory study in which we collected and analyzed the quality of the metadata and the usage, in terms of views and downloads, of approximately 400,000 datasets from 28 OGD portals. Our analysis based on five research questions focused on: 1 - The usage trends of OGD datasets measured in terms of Views and Downloads; 2 - The datasets metadata quality and compliance to FAIR; 3 - The relationship between datasets usage and their metadata quality and FAIR compliance; 4 - The relationship between datasets usage and datasets categorization; 5 - The relationship between datasets usage and some of their portals features.

Our investigation revealed three main findings. The first finding relating to RQ1 shows that datasets are mostly underused, albeit with relevant differences between the portals. As to RQ2, on the whole, OGD portals pay varying attention to the quality of the metadata of their datasets and their compliance with the FAIR principles. As to RQ3, our results show that by adopting our methodology, based on two existing quality assessment tools, the use of direct usage metrics, and applied to the 28 portals examined, we did not find a clear positive relationship between datasets usage and metadata quality. Accordingly, we recommend that such a relationship should not be assumed for granted. These findings led us to consider other factors that may influence the use of OGD datasets. To answer RQ4, taking into consideration the portals of 14 US cities, we have considered if datasets categorization can be a factor capable of directing users' interest. Statistical analysis confirmed this hypothesis,

also highlighting a disparity between the percentage of datasets published in a certain category and their use. Moreover, answering RQ5, we found a negative correlation between OGD portals' usage and the number of their datasets, while no other portals' demographic features considered correlate with datasets usage.

Our analysis, therefore, highlights the need to examine further factors that can determine the success of OGD datasets publishing policies and practices. This research can move in two directions. On the one hand, it may be useful to continue the investigation on the maturity and effectiveness of technologies to support the publication of data (e.g. the portals platforms, metadata modification tools, integration with social tools) correlating it with access and reuse of these data. On the other hand, to supply a more exhaustive usage assessment, surveys in the field could be carried out to analyze the effect on datasets usage of contextual aspects such as users' needs and competencies, also investigating the role and influence of indirect OGD usage modes.

A possible limitation of this work concerns the assessment of datasets' FAIR compliance and its relationship with their use. For the technical reasons mentioned, the analysis was applied to US citizen portals only, and involved a small sample of their datasets, for a total of 1120 datasets examined. That said, we believe that the sample of 80 datasets, selected for each portal, equally randomized between datasets below the first and above the third quartile, can provide reasonable population coverage and supports our findings.

From a practical perspective, based on our findings, and following the literature, we recommend portal managers and their political counterparts to constantly monitor the use of the published datasets through, at least, the basic parameters (usually provided by their platforms) that we use: Views and Downloads. Accurately monitoring and analyzing user behavior would have a twofold advantage for portal managers. First, having timely and punctual information on the success of individual datasets. Secondly, to be able to direct their publication efforts based on the greater or lesser popularity of certain categories. However, we point out that the adoption of the two metrics considered, if able to provide an overview of the use of the OGD datasets, is not sufficient alone to testify the impact of OGD

policies. This could be better photographed if detailed information on third-party applications reusing a dataset were also collected and published together with the dataset. Our work also wants to be a spur for portals managers to publish usage data along with the datasets. In fact, during the selection of the portals of our sample, we noticed the low propensity to publish such data, especially in most of the national portals. However, as noted by some authors, posting usage information can sometimes encourage potential users to access one portal's datasets at the expense of those from other portals with undisclosed usage data or showing low usage values.

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Appendix

The metadata quality assessment has been carried out, by applying the 17 metrics defined and described by Neumaier et al.²⁶, we summarized in Table 8. We followed their nomenclature for dimensions and metrics names, except for the *Spatial* and *Temporal* metrics, that they declared and implemented only in the ‘Open Data Portal Watch’ code.

Table 8. Metadata quality Dimensions and Metrics

Dimension	Metric	Goal
Existence	Access	Tests if metadata contains URIs to access and download the dataset
	Discovery	Tests if metadata contains a description and a title for the dataset and its resource files, and some keywords helping discovery the dataset
	Contact	Tests if there are information to contact the owner or the publisher
	Rights	Tests if license information is provided
	Preservation	Tests the existence of metadata information regarding the format, size, media type and the update frequency of the datasets
	Date	Tests if the dates of creation and modification of the metadata and the dataset are provided
	Spatial	Tests the existence of some spatial information (e.g. polygon, shape,...)
	Temporal	Tests the existence of some temporal information (e.g. start or end of the period of the time covered by the dataset)
Conformance	AccessURL	Tests the syntactical validity of the access URI
	ContactEmail	Tests the validity of contact email addresses
	ContactURL	Tests the validity of contact address URIs
	DateFormat	Tests if date is in a valid format
	License	Tests if the license maps to a list of license descriptions provided by the Open Definition
	FileFormat	Check the validity of the file format and media type against a list of registered formats and media types supplied by IANA
Data Open	OpenFormat	Tests if the dataset is supplied in open format
	MachineRead	Tests if the dataset is supplied in a machine readable format
	OpenLicense	Tests if the dataset is supplied according to an open license

The FAIR assessment has been carried out through the ‘FAIR Evaluator’ tool³⁰ via the 22 ‘Compliance Tests’ (aka *metrics*) implementing the ‘Maturity Indicator Tests’ defined and described in^{XXXI}, and summarized in Table 9. For each test it is also reported the identification of the corresponding FAIR sub-principle⁷³.

^{XXXI}<https://fairsharing.github.io/FAIR-Evaluator-FrontEnd/#!/collections/6>

Table 9. FAIR principles and metrics

Principle	Metric (sub-principle)	Goal
Findable	Unique Identifier (F1)	Tests if the metadata resource has a unique identifier.
	Identifier Persistence (F1)	Tests if the unique identifier of the metadata resource is likely to be persistent.
	Data Identifier Persistence (F1)	Tests if the unique identifier of the data resource is likely to be persistent.
	Structured Metadata (F2)	Tests whether a machine is able to find structured metadata.
	Grounded Metadata (F2)	Tests whether a machine is able to find 'grounded' metadata.
	Data Identifier Explicitly In Metadata (F3)	Tests if the metadata contains the unique identifier to the data.
	Metadata Identifier Explicitly In Metadata (F3)	Tests if the metadata contains the unique identifier to the metadata itself.
Accessible	Searchable in major search engine (F4)	Tests whether a machine is able to discover the resource by search, using Microsoft Bing
	Uses open free protocol for data retrieval (A1.1)	Tests if data may be retrieved by an open and free protocol
	Uses open free protocol for metadata retrieval (A1.1)	Tests if Metadata may be retrieved by an open and free protocol.
	Data authentication and authorization (A1.2)	Tests a discovered data GUID for the ability to implement authentication and authorization in its resolution protocol.
	Metadata authentication and authorization (A1.2)	Tests metadata GUID for the ability to implement authentication and authorization in its resolution protocol.
	Metadata Persistence (A2)	Test if the metadata contains a persistence policy, explicitly identified by a persistencePolicy key.
	Interoperable	Metadata Knowledge Representation Language (weak) (I1)
Metadata Knowledge Representation Language (strong) (I1)		Tests if the metadata uses a formal language broadly applicable for knowledge representation (any form of RDF will pass this test)
Data Knowledge Representation Language (weak) (I1)		Tests if the data uses a formal language broadly applicable for knowledge representation (Any form of structured data will pass this test)
Data Knowledge Representation Language (strong) (I1)		Tests if the data uses a formal language broadly applicable for knowledge representation (Any form of ontologically-grounded linked data will pass this test)
Metadata uses FAIR vocabularies (weak) (I2)		Tests if the linked data metadata uses terms that resolve.
Metadata uses FAIR vocabularies (strong) (I2)		Tests if the linked data metadata uses terms that resolve to linked (FAIR) data.
Metadata contains qualified outward references) (I3)		Tests if the metadata links outward to third-party resources.
Reusable	Metadata Includes License (weak) (R1.1)	Tests if the metadata contains an explicit pointer to the license.
	Metadata Includes License (strong) (R1.1)	Tests if the linked data metadata contains an explicit pointer to the license.